

eDemOS Deliberative Platform

Summary of Online Discussion on the Implementation
of Open Science in the Czech Republic

AMULET (Advanced MULTiscale materials for key Enabling Technologies)

November 2025

Michal Trčka, Vratislav Žabka

eDemOS Deliberative Platform

Summary of Online Discussion on the Implementation of Open Science in the Czech Republic

Summary of selected results of the sociological survey conducted as part of the OP JAK AMULET project using the eDemOS online discussion platform, accompanying activities of the public hearing [Making Sense of Open Science](#) (Prague, September 12, 2025).

Prepared by: Michal Trčka and Vratislav Žabka

Publication date: November 12, 2025

Version: 1.0

Language: English

Contact: michal.trcka@jh-inst.cas.cz

This work has been funded by a grant from the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558 Advanced MULTISCALE materials for key Enabling Technologies.

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Licence: CC BY 4.0](#)

Summary of Online Discussion Results	4
Introduction	8
1 Discussion Forum	9
1.1 Groups Based on Voting and Entry Questionnaire	10
1.2 Areas of Consensus	13
1.3 Areas of Division	16
2 Proposal Discussion	21
2.1 Proposal: Economically Sustainable Form of Open Access Publishing in the Czech Republic	21
2.1.1 Summary of Proposal	21
2.1.2 Voting Results	22
2.1.3 Comments	23
2.2 Proposal: Establishing the National Open Science Strategy in the Czech Republic	28
2.2.1 Summary of Proposal	28
2.2.2 Voting Results	28
2.2.3 Comments	29

Summary of Online Discussion Results

The online discussion via the deliberative platform eDemOS was an accompanying activity to the public hearing [Making Sense of Open Science](#) (Prague, September 12, 2025).

The discussion was held **from September 8, 2025, to October 20, 2025**.

Number of users: **233**

Link to the eDemOS platform in Czech and English:

<https://jurgen-habermas.jh-inst.cas.cz/amulet-main/>

Summary of Discussion Forum Results

A total of 131 respondents participated in the discussion forum (121 were included in the evaluation of results).

The difference between the groups does not lie in their inclusion in **OP JAK projects**,¹ but in their professional affiliation and their assessment of open data:

- **Group 1: “Open Data Optimists”**
84 respondents, representing 64.1% of all participants and 69.4% of those included in the evaluation of results.
- **Group 2: “Open Data Pessimists”**
37 respondents, representing 28.3% of all participants and 30.6% of those included in the evaluation of results.
This group consists mainly of academic staff, with lower representation from the social sciences and humanities.

The highest level of agreement among participants was recorded for the following questions (Cluster 1 – *Open Data Optimists* and Cluster 2 – *Open Data Pessimists*):

- 16. Czech researchers should have the same conditions for publishing in OA as their colleagues in Germany (capped APCs, the legal option to publish the AAM in a repository).
- 11. The application of open science principles in the Czech Republic is unclear. Different calls have different rules, and funding providers are not always sure what exactly they require.
- 19. The Czech Republic should have an overview of all forms of OA! Currently, NTK only collects information on APCs (gold/hybrid), while there is no record of green OA or diamond OA.
- 22. The funding of APCs is not adequately addressed in the Czech Republic.
- 20. The state should ensure an effective Rights Retention Strategy (e.g., through

¹ **OP JAK (Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský)** is a programme focused on supporting the development of education, research, development, and innovation in the Czech Republic. The structure of OP JAK reflects the priority themes funded by the European Union’s structural funds in the 2021–2027 programming period, as well as the experience gained from previous operational programmes under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports.

legislation). Responsibility should not be shifted onto individual researchers and institutions.

The most significant differences in responses between the groups were observed for the following questions, where Cluster 1 – **Open Data Optimists agreed**, while Cluster 2 – **Open Data Pessimists disagreed**:

- 1. Research data management and accessibility of research data should be a mandatory part of research projects and grants funded through targeted support.
- 2. A data management plan plays an essential role in the reproducibility and efficiency of scientific work, as it helps to plan data management systematically.
- 7. Open data helps strengthen public trust in science.
- 15. Open data serves as a resource for countering disinformation.
- 33. In a longer-term perspective, a data management plan makes researchers' work easier and ensures the traceability of results.

Differences in responses between the groups were also observed for the following questions, where Cluster 1 – **Open Data Optimists disagreed**, while Cluster 2 – **Open Data Pessimists agreed**:

- 3. Creating a Data Management Plan (DMP) is a time-consuming and unnecessary administrative formality that does not significantly benefit researchers.
- 13. Even if I strive for open data, no one will know the exact procedure, and it will not lead to the same results.

Summary of Proposal Discussions

Economically Sustainable Form of Open Access Publishing in the Czech Republic

Author: Roman Sobotka (The principal investigator of the OP JAK Photomachines project)

Summary of Proposal:

- If the provider insists on Open Access, they should accept the CC BY-NC-ND license.
- A reasonable compromise between the principles of open science and the economic dimension appears to be the requirement to publish in open form (freely downloadable PDF on the publisher's website or in a public repository) without further conditions.

Voting Results:

- **Agree: 122 voters (86%); Disagree: 10 voters (7%); Pass/Unsure: 10 voters (7%).**
- Among scientific and academic staff members, agreement with the proposal clearly predominates, regardless of involvement in OP JAK projects.

Summary of Comments:

- **Consensus that the current Open Access (OA) model is unsustainable; a systemic solution is needed** – legislative protection for authors, state and EU support for non-commercial publishing platforms, reform of research evaluation, and transparent financial flows.
- **Authors**, without any entitlement to remuneration, **transfer their property rights to publishers**, who then monetize research results through subscriptions, APC fees, or selling data to technology companies.
- **A major issue is the high Article Processing Charges (APCs)**, which are not systematically funded in the Czech Republic. Some participants call for APC caps.
- **Deeper systemic causes** include **pressure on bibliometrics and the evaluation of researchers based on quantity and impact factor**, which perpetuates dependence on commercial publishers.
- **Controversy over mandatory preprint publication**: criticism that these are unverified texts and compulsory publication may harm the quality of scientific communication; on the other hand, it enables rapid and open sharing of results.
- **Support for Diamond or Platinum OA journals** funded by institutions or EU funds, allowing publication without fees.
- Proposals **to introduce the Rights Retention Strategy** and legislative adjustment of **secondary publication rights**, following the example of Austria, Germany, or France.

Establishing the National Open Science Strategy in the Czech Republic

Author: Tereza Szybisty (OpenAIRE)

Summary of Proposal:

- This proposal aims to develop a comprehensive national open science strategy that will provide **a clear framework for the systematic anchoring of open science principles in the Czech Republic**, reflecting national specificities, while also aligning with European and global recommendations.
- The strategy must be **implementation-oriented**, including concrete measures in the areas of infrastructure, funding, education, and capacity building, as well as the allocation of responsibilities to individual stakeholders.
- An integral part of the proposal is also the introduction of **nationwide monitoring of the implementation and impact** of open science.

Voting Results:

- **Agree: 82 voters (73%); Disagree: 13 voters (11%); Pass/Unsure: 19 voters (16%).**
- Participants across professions mostly agreed. For "other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution," this agreement is unequivocal. Among "scientific and academic staff members", the number of people who indicate pass/unsure has increased compared to the first vote on the proposal.

Summary of Comments:

- **A different understanding of open science (OS)** exists in the Czech Republic compared to Western Europe; **a unified national strategy is needed** with goals such as openness, transparency, trustworthiness, and reducing dependence on commercial providers.
- **The core values of OS are clear, but the problem lies in implementation without regard to disciplinary specifics;** there is a risk that measures will be formal and of little benefit.
- **Lack of vision and purpose in implementation;** examples of a formal approach (e.g., secondary publication rights in the Czech version treated only as “deposit,” not actual publication).
- **Need for a national strategy and coordinated approach** – infrastructure, long-term funding, secure data sharing, and data protection.
- **Concerns about bureaucratization and centralization** – creating a new institution will not solve the problem; monitoring and metrics may lead to distortion (“you measure what you want to see”).
- **Warning against politicization:** the strategy should enhance scientific practice, not serve political goals; science is integral to competitiveness, so caution is necessary when handling knowledge.
- **Negotiate national specifics and avoid mechanically adopting EU directives; utilize the EOSC CZ framework** and develop it in line with European guidelines.

Introduction

The online discussion via the deliberative platform eDemOS was an accompanying activity to the public hearing [Making Sense of Open Science](#) (Prague, September 12, 2025), using three applications:

- **Discussion forum** / What people think about open science – in their own words.
- **Proposal Discussions** / Voting on proposals to improve the implementation of Open Science principles.
- **Imagine OS** / A card-based method for reflecting on open science.

The activity had two objectives:

- to use these tools to explore the attitudes of the broader academic community towards the implementation of selected principles of open science in the Czech Republic (principles and practices of data management, publishing regimes, and the public engagement in science), with a focus on assessing the current state and prospects for the future;
- to explore the potential of the eDemOS research tool and three different approaches to online participation, and assess the differences between these methods and the results obtained, as in projects such as [DEMOS](#).

The discussion was held **from September 8, 2025, to October 20, 2025**.

Number of users: **233**

Link to the eDemOS platform in Czech and English:

<https://jorgen-habermas.jh-inst.cas.cz/amulet-main/>

Link to the eDemOS platform website:

<https://e-demos.com/>

Participation was open to individuals aged 18 years or older. The study was completely anonymous; recorded responses are used exclusively for research purposes, and no third parties have access to the data. Results are published only in the form of statistical and qualitative analyses. Participants could withdraw from the study at any time simply by closing the browser window. Completing the questionnaire was not time-limited; participants could try one or more applications. No financial compensation was provided for participation in this study.

1 Discussion Forum

Inspired by the platform [Polis](#)

In the first application, participants encountered a series of (provocative) statements related to open science, particularly principles and practices of data management, publishing regimes, and public engagement in science. Voting itself was carried out by selecting one of three options: *Agree*, *Disagree*, *Pass/Unsure*.

The statements did not represent the organizers' views; other participants additionally submitted some. If participants had an opinion not reflected in any of the original statements, they could propose their own short statement for voting through the application. Thus, participants not only responded to existing statements but could actively add new ones, which other respondents then voted on.

After registering and logging in to the platform, participants were asked to complete a short questionnaire regarding several personal details. For the evaluation of the online discussion, the most relevant questions pertained to the respondent's profession and involvement in a project funded by the Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský (OP JAK).²

The graph shows the number of users by profession in each application. The discussions were attended primarily by respondents with the professions “scientific and academic staff member” and “other employee of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution.”

Abbreviations used:

- **academic** – scientific and academic staff memembr

² **OP JAK (Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský)** is a programme focused on supporting the development of education, research, development, and innovation in the Czech Republic. The structure of OP JAK reflects the priority themes funded by the European Union’s structural funds in the 2021–2027 programming period, as well as the experience gained from previous operational programmes under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports.

- **AVCR** – other employee of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution
- **student** – university student
- **VaVal** – employee of a Research, Development, and Innovation support provider (outside the CAS)
- **administr.** – other employee of the state administration
- **other** – other employee of the state administration

1.1 Groups Based on Voting and Entry Questionnaire

During the evaluation, users who answered fewer than 10 questions were excluded, as were questions that were answered by fewer than one-third of respondents.

- A total of 131 respondents participated in the discussion forum.
- Of these, 10 respondents (7.6%) were excluded due to a low number of responses.

The difference between the groups does not lie in their inclusion in OP JAK projects, but in their professional affiliation and their assessment of open data:

- **Group 1: “Open Data Optimists”**
84 respondents, representing 64.1% of all participants and 69.4% of those included in the evaluation of results.
- **Group 2: “Open Data Pessimists”**
37 respondents, representing 28.3% of all participants and 30.6% of those included in the evaluation of results.
This group consists mainly of scientific and academic staff members, with lower representation from the social sciences and humanities.

The graph shows the distribution of respondents by profession. It clearly illustrates the minimal representation of the profession "other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution" in Group 2.

Groups (**clusters**) 1 and 2 represent two main typologies of participants: Group 1, *Open Data Optimists*, and Group 2, *Open Data Pessimists*.

The graph shows the distribution of respondents by specialization among scientific and academic staff members. It clearly highlights the minimal representation of the fields "Social Sciences" and "Humanities" in Group 2.

Groups (**clusters**) 1 and 2 represent two main typologies of participants: Group 1, *Open Data Optimists*, and Group 2, *Open Data Pessimists*.

Abbreviations used:

- **spec** – Specialization of scientific and academic staff members
- **others** – "Mathematical and Physical Sciences", "Chemical Sciences", "Biological and Medical Sciences", "Engineering and Technology", "Earth and Environmental Sciences"
- **soc/hum** – „Social Sciences“ and „Humanities“

The graph illustrates the influence of individual questions on dividing respondents into two groups. The arrows represent the importance of the questions for cluster formation—their length corresponds to the degree of influence, and their direction shows how the question contributes to distinguishing the groups.

For example, questions 7 and 3 point directly opposite each other, which means that both have a substantial impact on group separation, but respondents answered them in opposite ways. Conversely, questions 16, 19, and 20 point in a direction where the groups do not significantly diverge, and therefore have only a minor influence on their division. This result corresponds to the meaning of the stated questions and the previous graphs.

From the perspective of influence, the questions can be divided as follows:

- **Strong influence in one direction:** 1, 2, 7, 9, 14, 15, 21, 33, 36
- **Strong influence in the opposite direction:** 3, 4, 10, 12, 13, 26, 42
- **Almost no influence:** arrows pointing straight down

1.2 Areas of Consensus

In these graphs, the average responses of all participants within the given cluster are displayed. These graphs allow us not only to compare the degree of similarity between the responses of both clusters but also to assess the extent to which participants agreed with individual statements.

For example, in question no. 11. Both clusters show a high level of agreement, with Cluster 1 agreeing slightly less. Conversely, in question no. 32 both clusters responded similarly, but with a significantly higher proportion of “pass/unsure” answers or missing data, which makes sense, as this was one of the last questions in the discussion forum.

Points of consensus

The highest level of agreement among participants was recorded for the following questions (Cluster 1 – *Open Data Optimists* and Cluster 2 – *Open Data Pessimists*):

16. Czech researchers should have the same conditions for publishing in OA as their colleagues in Germany (capped APCs, the legal option to publish the AAM in a repository).

11. The application of open science principles in the Czech Republic is unclear. Different calls have different rules, and funding providers are not always sure what exactly they require.

19. The Czech Republic should have an overview of all forms of OA! Currently, NTK only collects information on APCs (gold/hybrid), while there is no record of green OA or diamond OA.

22. The funding of APCs is not adequately addressed in the Czech Republic.

20. The state should ensure an effective Rights Retention Strategy (e.g., through legislation). Responsibility should not be shifted onto individual researchers and institutions.

1.3 Areas of Division

The graph clearly shows which questions exhibit the most significant differences between the clusters. For the pair of questions no. 13 and 15, the clusters responded almost oppositely, similar to questions no. 3 and 7. Significant differences also appeared in questions no. 1 and 2.

Points of division

The most significant differences in responses between the groups were observed for the following questions, where Cluster 1 – **Open Data Optimists** agreed, while Cluster 2 – **Open Data Pessimists** disagreed:

1. Research data management and accessibility of research data should be a mandatory part of research projects and grants funded through targeted support.

2. A data management plan plays an essential role in the reproducibility and efficiency of scientific work, as it helps to plan data management systematically.

7. Open data helps strengthen public trust in science.

15. Open data serves as a resource for countering disinformation.

33. In a longer-term perspective, a data management plan makes researchers' work easier and ensures the traceability of results.

Differences in responses between the groups were also observed for the following questions, where Cluster 1 – **Open Data Optimists disagreed**, while Cluster 2 – **Open Data Pessimists agreed**:

3. Creating a Data Management Plan (DMP) is a time-consuming and unnecessary administrative formality that does not significantly benefit researchers.

13. Even if I strive for open data, no one will know the exact procedure, and it will not lead to the same results.

2 Proposal Discussion

Inspired by the platform [Decidim](#)

Voting on proposals to improve the implementation of Open Science principles:

- *Economically Sustainable Form of Open Access Publishing in the Czech Republic*
- *Establishing the National Open Science Strategy in the Czech Republic*

In the first vote, participants had the opportunity to review a specific proposal for changing requirements related to open access publishing, which was addressed to grant providers in the Czech Republic. In the second vote, they expressed their views on a proposal to create a comprehensive national open science strategy.

It is essential to note that these proposals do not reflect the organizers' position, but instead were prepared by other participants in the public hearing, *Making Sense of Open Science*.

The voting itself consisted of selecting one of three options:

Agree, Disagree, Pass/Unsure.

Additionally, participants could share their opinions on the topic through a short comment, which was visible to other participants.

2.1 Proposal: Economically Sustainable Form of Open Access Publishing in the Czech Republic

Author: Roman Sobotka (The principal investigator of the OP JAK Photomachines project)

2.1.1 Summary of Proposal

In 2021, the European Commission (EC) and the European Research Council (ERC) tightened the publishing requirements following the cOAlition-S initiative. Discussions about the appropriateness of the high costs of article processing charges (APCs) are now resonating in the Czech Republic, especially after the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports introduced the obligation to use the CC-BY license in OP JAK Excellent Research projects. The demands of some publishers are financially unrealistic for the Czech Republic.

Suppose the situation with publication fees does not radically change in the future. In that case, Czech research funding providers (ministries, GAČR, TAČR, etc.) should not require CC-BY licensing as a condition for recognizing publications. If the provider insists on Open Access, they should accept the CC-BY-NC-ND license. This license does not restrict the sharing of the work, except for using results for commercial purposes (NC) or creating modified versions (ND). However, with some publishers, the CC-BY-NC-ND license does not prevent the payment of high APCs.

A reasonable compromise between the principles of open science and the economic dimension appears to be the requirement to publish in open form (freely downloadable PDF on the publisher's website or in a public repository) without further conditions. This

formulation would also allow the opening (and recognition) of a publication after the end of a publication embargo during the lifetime of a project. Although this would not constitute open access stricto sensu (immediate free access upon article acceptance), all results and data of the research project would be accessible to anyone no later than the project's completion date.

A detailed description of the proposal is available in the application.

2.1.2 Voting Results

- **Responded:** 142 participants
- **Agreed:** 122 participants; **Disagreed:** 10; **Passed/Unsure:** 10.

More detailed results show the level of **agreement among participants** who indicated that they are “scientific and academic staff members” and “involved in a project funded by the Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský (OP JAK).” Only two of these participants abstained from voting, while **64 agreed**.

For participants who were “involved in a project funded by the Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský (OP JAK)” and “other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution,” **16 agreed, 5 disagreed, and 3 abstained**.

Among participants who are “scientific and academic staff members” but **not part of OP JAK projects, almost all agreed (36)**.

For participants categorized as “other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution,” **4 agreed, 3 abstained, and 1 disagreed**.

2.1.3 Comments

The discussion on the proposal centered on the current model of open publishing (Open Access), its economic implications, and the relationships between authors, publishers, and institutions. The prevailing view is critical of the commercial system of scientific publishing, which, according to most participants with comments, results in the transfer of public funds into the private hands of publishers. It is repeatedly mentioned that authors often surrender their proprietary rights to publishers without compensation, who then monetize research results through subscriptions, APC fees, or by selling data to technology companies.

A fundamental issue is the high article processing charges (APCs), for which there is no systemic funding mechanism in the Czech Republic. Participants note that APC prices do not reflect the actual value of services provided by publishers and that the current model is economically unsustainable—some call for **capping APCs** or creating a competitive environment among publishers. As a long-term solution, **support for Diamond or Platinum OA journals** funded by institutions or European funds is repeatedly proposed, enabling publication without fees.

Licensing and authors' rights are also strong themes. The transfer of exclusive rights to publishers (e.g., under CC BY-NC-ND) is criticized for weakening authors' positions and limiting their ability to manage their own work. Many comments suggest **introducing a Rights Retention Strategy** and legislative adjustments for secondary publication rights, following the examples of Austria, Germany, or France, to strengthen Green OA and reduce publisher monopolies.

The requirement for mandatory preprint publication is also a matter of controversy. Some participants note that preprints often represent unverified or immature texts, and mandatory publication could harm the quality of scientific communication. Others see them as a reasonable compromise that enables rapid and open sharing of results.

Several participants highlight **deeper systemic causes of the problem**—primarily the **pressure of bibliometrics and evaluation of researchers based on quantity and impact factor**, which perpetuates dependence on commercial publishers. Discussants therefore propose reforming the research evaluation system and placing greater emphasis on content quality rather than journal prestige.

Overall, there is **a broad consensus that the current OA model is unsustainable.** The solution should be systemic—covering legislative protection for authors, state and EU support for non-commercial publishing platforms, reform of research evaluation, and transparent financial flows.

Individual comments

2025-10-13 As long as where and how much one publishes carries almost the same weight as what one publishes, nothing will change. Why would publishers cut their margins when there's no risk of losing submissions? Paying APCs is considered a problem, but pouring billions of taxpayers' money into subscriptions isn't? The scientific community rejects cheap open-access publishing alternatives because it's primarily about prestige, and only secondarily about the dissemination of knowledge.

2025-10-10 APC fees and the dependence on private publishing companies represent a complete failure of science management. Easing Open Access conditions and limiting the payment of excessive APCs is the first step. The next step should be to put pressure on publishers, or, if necessary, for researchers to collectively resign from editorial boards and to establish new Open Access journals under the umbrella of academic institutions, with

very low APCs. However, it must be acknowledged that this would lead to the collapse of scientometrics based on the Impact Factor (IF).

2025-10-09 Yes, the proposal is entirely logical and feasible; unfortunately, the current situation only leads to the spending of enormous amounts of financial resources — completely unnecessarily.

2025-10-08 The problem has been growing for at least 20 years (see <https://informationr.net/ir/9-2/paper170.html>). Yet we still fail to address the root causes, which lie in the almost psychotic pressure of bibliometric evaluation. The profits from open-access APCs of prestigious publishers have multiplied, exceeding 2.5 billion USD by 2023 (see <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2025/09/11/shaking-up-the-scholarly-publishing-market-why-caps-on-apcs-could-backfire/>). Why would they change anything, when we voluntarily guarantee their control over the very metrics that define scientific prestige?

2025-10-08 “...a reasonable compromise between the principles of open science and economic sustainability...” — Do I understand correctly that this compromise still involves fees of 1–5 thousand EUR for roughly a 15-page PDF, with only a change in licensing rights? As scientists, we are funded by taxpayers, we review for free (and polish our own manuscripts, meaning the publisher’s actual work is minimal), yet thousands of euros are charged for a ~15-page PDF — just so the taxpayer can read what they already paid for through our salaries? I don’t claim to have a solution, but the publishers’ profit margins seem immoral to me.

2025-10-08 I strongly agree that publishing on a preprint server is a sensible compromise. Changes made to the final published article are usually at the level of typos, language editing etc. and do not impact the published science. Paying thousands of Euros for these scientifically unimportant modifications is wasting money that would be better spent on funding research, not publishers.

2025-10-02 I completely agree that OA is just a way of funneling public money into private pockets. The author creates a work, transfers the rights to the publisher, and then pays for its publication... Imagine how that would work with a song ;-) Chinasky writes a new song, transfers the rights to a publisher, pays for its release, and then the publisher distributes the song... I suggest that authors of scientific publications should also fall under OSA (<https://www.osa.cz> ;-))

2025-10-02 I like open access to articles, but I dislike the financial flows associated with it. As long as the evaluation of research depends on the journal in which you publish, publishers set the rules and we adapt to them. I would prefer a system where this financial flow is interrupted. For example, mandatory publication of preprints + data + code (with points awarded for that), more points for diamond and green OA, and a price cap on APCs.

Would it not be possible to create a competitive environment among publishers to put pressure on lowering APCs?

[2025-10-01](#) In my opinion, the problem of high APCs should be addressed by transitioning to platinum open access [diamond OA], thereby bypassing private publishing houses. I acknowledge that the drawback of this solution is that its implementation will take a long time and requires European consensus. For example, the European Union could support disciplinary organizations (such as the European Mathematical Society) in establishing Open Access journals in which European authors could publish without APCs, with the operating costs of these journals covered by the EU.

[2025-09-23](#) The author is responsible for publications. A compromise between protection and openness, i.e. a detailed publication strategy with justification according to the rule "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," should be defined by the beneficiary. Its adequacy should be assessed and decided on a case-by-case basis by the provider, and it should form part of the support agreement. I strongly disagree with the formalization and with the last paragraph, which creates a "hybrid creature," trying to shirk responsibility and cheat the system.

[2025-09-18](#) I resonate with the comment from [2025-09-11](#) and I see nothing else in this issue but a torrent of public money flowing into the private pockets of publishers. It is surprising that, apart from scientists, it seems to bother no one. I'm sorry.

[2025-09-12](#) The problem with licenses lies in the transfer of proprietary rights to the publisher. By assigning a CC BY-NC-ND license, the rights are typically transferred to the publisher (for free!!!), who then applies the licenses, and the author may end up cutting themselves off from their own publication. By choosing a stricter license, the author does not protect their rights; the future of the article is not decided by them, but by the publisher.

[2025-09-12](#) I support the initiative, but I lean more toward the already mentioned systemic solution of introducing a Rights Retention Strategy at the national level.

[2025-09-11](#) Interestingly, nobody seems to mind that publishers receive research results for free – including the exclusive rights (!!) – process them, and then sell them back. Their reluctance to assign works a CC BY license is only a logical consequence – it reduces the value of their new property. With CC BY-NC-ND, the publishers' rights (acquired for free through transfer from the authors) are not weakened as much. And so Elsevier can present itself as a "source of health" information for Apple, Taylor & Francis can sell data to Microsoft for \$10M to train AI, and so on.

[2025-09-10](#) Regarding the issue of preprints: the pressure to publish them seems unnecessary to me, because the information they contain cannot be fully relied upon anyway. At best, they are immature versions of manuscripts that may still undergo

significant changes (for example, as a result of constructive reviewer feedback). At worst, they are papers that, for various reasons, will never make it through the peer-review process, or only appear in one of the predatory journals. Green OA seems to be a better path toward open yet serious science.

[2025-09-10](#) Good morning, The proposal is simple and practical. I definitely agree. Josef Šivic

[2025-09-10](#) The problematic aspect of this proposal is that, in this way, rights are/will be transferred to publishers (exclusive licence). A more suitable, systematic solution would be the implementation of a Rights Retention Strategy at the national level. Ideally, this would be achieved through the introduction of a so-called secondary publication right (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Spain...), which would truly pave the way for Green OA.

[2025-09-10](#) In addition to the unreasonable requirement for CC BY, another problem is the requirement to publish preprints in repositories (i.e., for example, a version of an article that has just been submitted for peer review). I can point out several reasons why this may not be desirable. Another unreasonable requirement is to publish in a repository (e.g., arXiv) the accepted version of an article that is already published as OA. Once an article is OA at the publisher, it does not need to (and probably should not) be posted elsewhere.

[2025-09-10](#) The main problem lies in the fees for Open Access publishing (APC). We should choose a journal primarily based on its relevance and expected impact. However, funding for APCs is not systematically addressed in the Czech Republic.

Example (International Journal of Theoretical Physics at CTU):

The institution has tokens to cover the fees, but

- at the beginning of the year, they are not yet allocated,
- by May, they are already used up for the rest of the year.

Even the rules for Open Access are complex and confusing, and we should not waste time studying them in detail.

[2025-09-09](#) Systemic solution would mainly be targeted support for publishers of Diamond OA journals and limiting the influence of commercial publishers.

2.2 Proposal: Establishing the National Open Science Strategy in the Czech Republic

Author: Tereza Szybisty (OpenAIRE)

2.2.1 Summary of Proposal

This proposal aims to develop a comprehensive National Open Science Strategy that will provide a clear framework for the systematic anchoring of open science principles in the Czech Republic. The Strategy should define the core values and objectives of open science in line with European and global recommendations while reflecting national specificities, needs, and individual stakeholders' readiness levels.

The Strategy must be implementation-oriented. In addition to political objectives, it should include concrete measures in the areas of infrastructure (data and publishing), funding, education, and capacity building, including the allocation of responsibilities to individual stakeholders.

An integral part of the requirement to create the National Open Science Strategy should also be the introduction of nationwide monitoring of the implementation and impact of Open Science in the Czech Republic.

A detailed description of the proposal is available in the application.

2.2.2 Voting Results

- **Responded:** 114 participants
- **Agreed:** 82 participants; **Disagreed:** 13; **Passed/Unsure:** 19

For this proposal, no statistically significant difference in voting was observed between the various professional groups. Participants across professions mostly agreed with the proposal. Among "other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution", this agreement was unequivocal. Among "scientific and academic staff members", a higher percentage of "pass" or "unsure" responses was observed compared to the first topic.

A more detailed analysis shows agreement among participants who indicated that they are:

“Involved in a project funded by the Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský (OP JAK)” and at the same time “other employee of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution”: **Agreed: 20, Disagreed: 2, Abstained: 1.**

“Scientific and academic staff members” involved in an OP JAK project: **Agreed: 35, Disagreed: 6, Abstained: 10.**

“Scientific and academic staff members” not involved in OP JAK projects: **Agreed: 18, Disagreed: 5, Abstained: 7.**

“Other employees of a university, the Czech Academy of Sciences, or another research institution” not involved in OP JAK projects: **Agreed: 5, Disagreed: 0, Abstained: 0.**

2.2.3 Comments

The discussion focuses on **the differing understandings of open science in the Czech Republic** compared to Western Europe (e.g., the Netherlands, France) and on **the need for a unified national strategy** that clearly defines its goals—not only openness, but also

transparency, trustworthiness, and reducing dependence on commercial providers. There is broad agreement that **the core values of open science are clear; the problem lies in how they are implemented without considering disciplinary specifics**, which can lead to formal and ineffective measures.

Concerns about bureaucratization and purposeless monitoring are repeatedly raised, as these could bring more administrative burden than benefit. Participants warn that tracking indicators instead of qualitative evaluation may distort results (“you measure what you want to see, not what you hope for”). **Centralization efforts are also criticized**—the creation of a new institution does not solve the problem and may lead to more bureaucracy and politicization of science.

Comments emphasize the need for a clear vision and purpose behind the open science strategy. Often, there is a lack of understanding of why measures are introduced, resulting in formal implementations with little real impact—for example, secondary publication rights in the Czech version are treated in legislation merely as “deposit” rather than genuine publication. Positive examples from abroad are also mentioned: the French *Open Science Monitor* study shows that open science increases research impact—open access publications have, on average, 8.6% more citations, data sharing 14.3%, code sharing 13.5%, and preprints 19%, with effects varying by discipline (e.g., +34.9% in healthcare).

Creating a National Open Science Strategy is considered key, enabling infrastructure development, long-term funding, and **a coordinated approach** to data and digital objects at both national and European levels, including secure sharing and protection. However, there is a warning about **the risk of politicizing the entire process**—the goal should be to improve scientific practice and increase impact, not to fulfill political declarations.

Science is also viewed as a key component of national and European competitiveness, so caution is advised when handling knowledge and data (e.g., during foreign project evaluations). Discussants mostly agree that **the Czech Republic should implement European directives about its own specifics**, avoid being “more papal than the Pope,” and **build on the existing EOSC CZ framework**, which provides the necessary foundation for developing open science.

Individual comments

2025-10-10 It can be useful — but only if it does not create yet another unreasonable bureaucratic burden for researchers. For example, it would be counterproductive if the Ministry of Education (MŠMT), the Research, Development and Innovation Council (RVVI), or another central administrator were to require institutions to collect and report quantitative and qualitative aspects of Open Science for all their publications on their own.

2025-10-09 That is precisely what the EOSC CZ should aim for — it is sufficient to implement the EU directive and negotiate the national specifics.

2025-10-08 It says here: “...in addition to political goals, it must include concrete measures...” — I’m concerned about the mention of political goals. From such a strategy, I would expect improvements in the functioning of the research system, increased impact, and similar outcomes. Science is also a key component of national (and European) competitiveness — we should be careful with how we handle the know-how generated here. Even sending GAČR project proposals abroad for evaluation carries a certain risk — a potential outflow of ideas. We could learn from the West and avoid being “more papal than the Pope”.

2025-09-23 The creation of a National Open Science Strategy is a fundamental prerequisite for building the necessary infrastructure and ensuring its sustainable funding. A coordinated approach to sharing data and digital objects on a national (or European) Open Science platform will provide a secure environment for storing and sharing data, including their long-term preservation.

2025-09-22 I agree with the need to create an open science strategy. It seems to me that one of the major problems of open science in the Czech Republic is the lack of a vision of what we are doing and why we are doing it. As a result, instead of implementing ideas, we are just putting letters into the law. That is why in the new research law, the secondary publishing rights are “implemented” only as deposit in a repository, and the option of actual publication is completely missing — because apparently no one knows why it is being implemented, we are just ticking the box that “we have it.”

2025-09-18 “French study: Open science increases research impact by up to several tens of percent. The effect varies by discipline – for example, in healthcare data sharing leads to as much as +34.9% more citations, in biology preprints +25.3%, and in the social sciences code sharing +38%. Open science thus contributes to transparency, broader dissemination of knowledge, and greater international impact of scientific results. Source: link in the previous comment.

2025-09-18 The findings of a study by the French Open Science Monitor, which tracked more than 500,000 articles, show that open science significantly increases the visibility of research: open access publications receive on average 8.6% more citations, code sharing 13.5% more, data sharing 14.3% more, and the publication of preprints as much as 19% more.

Source:

<https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/for-the-first-time-on-a-scale-of-a-country-france-a-study-demonstrates-that-open-science-could-increase-the-chances-for-researchers-to-be-cited/>

2025-09-11 The understanding of open science in the Czech Republic differs from its understanding in, for example, the Netherlands or France – a unified policy or strategy would help define the broader goals of the whole process. For instance, it is not only about openness but also about transparency, trustworthiness, and, last but not least, reducing

dependence on commercial service providers. Monitoring is generally fine, but one must be careful about the nature of metrics – you get what you ask for, not what you wish for.

2025-09-10 There is no need to redefine the core values and goals – those are already defined and generally agreed upon. The problem arises with how to achieve these goals in different fields. As usual, when something is implemented top-down, in a general way, without knowledge of the specifics of various disciplines, the result is an unworkable mishmash. The requirements must have logic and purpose; otherwise, most people will approach them with a “have your cake and eat it too” attitude, and the benefit for science will be minimal. The contribution of monitoring will be negligible – just more bureaucracy.

2025-09-10 More bureaucracy and politics in science. I don't think everything has to be managed at a 'central' level. We've already had that.

2025-09-10 Creating a new institution does not mean solving the problem.

2025-09-09 In principle, it is a good direction, but the part concerning monitoring and evaluation is debatable, as it must not degenerate into another task and burden for scientific institutions, into self-serving reporting, or lead to simplistic interpretations. It is certainly appropriate to observe the impacts of OS; however, in general, monitoring “indicators” instead of conducting qualitative evaluation is always problematic in science.